

The NEX-100 Detector

Searching for $0\nu\beta\beta$ with a High Pressure Xenon TPC

Joshua Grocott, on behalf of the NEX collaboration

The Nature of the Neutrino

- Dirac neutrinos:
 - Particles are distinct from their antiparticles
 - Mass arises solely via interaction with the Higgs (tiny Yukawa coupling)
- Majorana neutrinos:
 - The neutrino is its own antiparticle
 - Introduction of heavy right handed neutrino provides a natural explanation for small mass in processes like the seesaw mechanism

Neutrinoless Double Beta Decay

- $0\nu\beta\beta$ would prove Majorana nature
- Lepton number violation $\Delta L = 2$
- A few possible isotopes, each with pros and cons- find the one that suits the technology

NEXT Technologies

High Pressure gaseous ^{136}Xe

Electroluminescent amplification

Radiopure PMTs

$$\Delta E < 1\% @ Q_{\beta\beta}$$

TPB coated SiPMs

Topological background discrimination

NEXT Timeline

PROTOTYPES

2009/2014

Demonstration of the detector concept

NEXT-WHITE

(NEW)

2015/2021

Background model assessment
 $2\nu\beta\beta$ measurement for ^{136}Xe

@ Laboratorio Subterráneo Canfranc

NEXT-100

2024/2030

Scalability

Background improvement
Neutrinoless double beta decay search in ^{136}Xe

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NEXT-HD

~2030

Neutrinoless double beta decay search through inverted neutrino mass ordering

NEXT-BOLD

Barium tagging for background-free experiment
inverted neutrino mass ordering

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NEXT-White (NEW)

- $\sim 5\text{kg}$ of ^{136}Xe
- 12 PMTs and 1792 SiPMs
- Objectives:
 - Background measurement
 - Low Energy Calibration
 - Energy resolution near $Q_{\beta\beta}$
 - Track characterisation for background rejection
 - Half life measurement and limit for $2\nu\beta\beta$ and $0\nu\beta\beta$, respectively

NEXT-White (NEW)

- $\sim 5\text{kg}$ of ^{136}Xe
- 12 PMTs and 1792 SiPMs
- Objectives:
 - **Background measurement** [Phys.Rev.C 105 \(2022\) 5, 055501](#)
 - Low Energy Calibration [JINST 13 P10014](#)
 - Energy resolution near $Q_{\beta\beta}$ [JHEP 10 \(2019\) 230](#)
 - Track characterisation for background rejection [Phys.Rev.C 105 \(2022\) 5, 055501](#)
 - **Half life measurement and limit for $2\nu\beta\beta$ and $0\nu\beta\beta$, respectively** [JHEP 09 \(2023\) 190](#)

NEXT-White Final Results for $\beta\beta$ Searches

Model-independent background subtraction

Enriched xenon

Depleted xenon

$0\nu\beta\beta$ searches

$$T_{1/2}^{2\nu\beta\beta} = 2.34^{+0.80}_{-0.46} \times 10^{21} \text{ yrs}$$

$$T_{1/2}^{0\nu\beta\beta} > 1.3 \times 10^{24} \text{ yrs}$$

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The NEXT-100 Detector

- Scales up NEW 1:2:
 - ~5 kg -> ~100 kg xenon
 - 12 -> 60 PMTs
 - 1792 -> 3584 SiPMs
- Objectives:
 - Further demonstrate scalability of NEXT technologies
 - Improve Radioactive budget
 - Demonstrate an energy resolution < 1% at $Q_{\beta\beta}$
 - Competitive search for $0\nu\beta\beta$ (sensitivity > 10^{25} years after 3 years)

JHEP 05 (2016)

arXiv:2505.17848v2

NEXT-100 Assembly

Tracking Plane

Field Cage

JINST 19 P02007

Cathode

Energy Plane

Joshua Grocott

arXiv:2505.01002v3

EL Region

The NEXT-100 Detector

Commissioning with Alphas

^{222}Rn energy spectrum

^{222}Rn emanates from cold getter- 3 alpha populations

arXiv:2505.17848v2

Electron transport

Electron lifetime = 57 ± 3 ms

Calibration with ^{83m}Kr

Geometrical Corrections

- ^{83m}Kr deployed via gas system, diffuses through active volume
- Point-like deposits of 41.5 keV

arXiv:2511.01710v1

Energy resolution

4.37% FWHM @ 41.5keV

High Energy

Energy resolution

^{228}Th source used via calibration ports

^{208}Tl peak

0.90% FWHM @ 2615 keV

arXiv:2511.02467v2

Topology

Single electron candidate

Electron-positron candidate

Radon Background

Internal

- ^{222}Rn decay product, ^{214}Bi , measured at cathode (1.17 Hz)
- Background suppressed by fiducialisation

External

Radon Abatement System (RAS) delivers radon free air to NEXT-100 lead castle

Going Forward with NEXT-100

- Soon to restart at high pressure (~10 bar)
- Reinforcement of Energy Plane currently underway
- Assess background model
- Measurement for $2\nu\beta\beta$ half life
- Searches for $0\nu\beta\beta$

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Barium tagging for background-free experiment inverted

Tonne Scale

[1] JINST 11 P12011 (2016)
 [2] Phys. Rev. Lett. 120, 132504 (2018)
 [3] Sci. Rep. 9: 15097 (2019)
 [4] Nature 583, 48 (2020)
 RSC Appl. Interfaces, 2, 185–199 (2025)
 [5] ACS Sensors 6, 1, 192–20 (2021)
 [6] 10.26434/chemrxiv-2023-wxpbh (2023)
 [7] ACS Sensors 2025, 10, 4, 2487–2498 (2025)

NEXT-HD

Projected 2030s

- **Mass:** ~ 1000kg at 15 bar
- **Sensitivity:** 1.2×10^{27} years after 5 years
- **Background:** 0.01 counts/ (keV ton year)

NEXT-BOLD

Summary

- NEXT High pressure TPCs are demonstrated as a technology for $0\nu\beta\beta$ searches
- NEXT-100 Low pressure run a success:
 - Electron properties characterised using alphas
 - Low energy calibration completed with ^{83m}Kr
 - Energy resolution $< 1\%$ @ $Q_{\beta\beta}$
 - Radon background characterised
- Ready for high pressure run
- NEXT-100 will be used as a powerful workbench for the tonne scale
- Tonne scale and barium tagging are on their way

Backup Slides

NEW Energy Resolution

Energy measurement with ^{208}Tl

Energy resolution $< 1\%$ @ $\approx Q_{\beta\beta}$

JINST 13 P10014

Commissioning with Alphas

Rb Decay Chain

Calibration with ^{83m}Kr

Tonne Scale Sensitivity

